

Strengthening Effect and Interfacial Adhesion of Boron and Silicon Carbide Fibre Reinforced Aluminum

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INTRODUCTION

Precondition for successful fibre reinforcement is a sufficient adhesion between fibre and matrix. Strong adhesion can be achieved by means of chemical reactions within the interface between fibre and matrix.

In case of boron or silicon carbide fibre reinforced aluminum the interfacial reactions occur during composite fabrication at high temperatures. These reactions can cause also fibre damage, however. To achieve sufficient adhesion without fibre damage fabrication conditions have to be controlled carefully, which vary with the several fabrication techniques as well as with the different types of boron and silicon carbide fibres.

The resulting strengthening effect is derived from flexural strength measurements, the resulting interfacial adhesion from shear strength tests.

The present paper reports on preparation and characterization of aluminum composites unidirectionally reinforced with boron and silicon carbide fibres.

EXPERIMENTAL AND EVALUATION METHODS

Fabrication and Testing of UD-model composites

Table 1 shows the four techniques which have been used for the fabrication of the model composites in form of aluminum sheets (~ 1 mm thick) and plates (~ 4 mm thick). Commercially available plasma sprayed tapes are applied for the braze bonding (Al_B , see part a) and the diffusion bonding process (Al_D , see part c).

In case of the foil filament process (Al_F , see part d) which is in principle also a diffusion technique, a sandwich of alternatively arranged fibre laminates and aluminum foils is sintered together by hot pressing.

Fig.1

Fabrication techniques, varied fabrication conditions and used fibre types

The so-called liquid infiltration process (Al_I , part b of Fig.1) is based on partial melting of the aluminum matrix which fills the slits and pores between the fibre layers. The structural arrangement of the fibres is preserved by the part of aluminum remaining unmolten and by the applied mechanical pressure.

The used types of fibres, the composition of the matrix and the varied fabrication conditions for the composites are also specified in Fig.1. In the following a short description of the composites is used which contains short name of the fibre type and the short name of the fabrication technique (e.g. B_{SiC}/Al_I = silicon carbide coated boron fibre reinforced aluminum fabricated by liquid infiltration process; or SiC/Al_F = silicon carbide fibre (on carbon substrate) reinforced aluminum fabricated by foil filament process).

The following fabrication and testing conditions were applied for all samples:

Fibre content by volume	: 46 % \pm 3
Dimensions of fabricated composites	: 40 x 60 mm x thicken.
Dimensions of test specimens	
for flexural test ($l/d = 30$)	: 1 x 4 x 50 mm
for short beam shear test ($l/d=5$)	: 4 x 4 x 25 mm
for symmetric block shear test (1)	: 6 x 6 x thickness

Calculation of Theoretical Composite Strength

The strengthening effect is usually derived from the ratio of the measured and the precalculated composite strength. For such precalculation one uses the rule of mixtures, supposing a uniform strength distribution of the single fibre (2). This precondition was not given in case of the boron and silicon carbide fibres, used in this study (fig.2).

It was necessary therefore to consider the strength distribution of the fibres. The effective fibre strength was derived from the bundle strength (σ_{b1} in fig.2) at the critical fibre length. The critical length was calculated by the ratio of fibre radius and measured shear strength of the composite. Additionally, the fracture behaviour of composites was to be taken into account: in case of brittle fracture only the value of the tension when first failure of a fibre in a bundle occurred was used as fibre strength (sign + in fig. 2).

Fig. 2

Tensile strength properties of used boron and silicon carbide fibres

The results of the calculations of theoretical composite strength are shown in fig. 3 based on the fibre properties compiled in fig. 2. The upper limit of each composite strength is based on the fibre bundle strength, the lower on the fibre strength resulting from the stress of first fibre failure. The precalculated composite strength increases with improved shear strength of the composites because the critical fibre length used in the calculation diminishes and thus the effective fibre strength increases.

Fig. 3

Theoretically calculated composite strength as function of shear strength (based on fibre strengths compiled in fig. 2)

For testing the applicability of this method fibres were separated from the fabricated composites by dissolving of the matrix. The mechanical properties (tensile strength and coefficient of variation) of the fibres and the shear strength of the composite were used for precalculation of the composite strength and compared with the measured composite strength. A good accordance between both was found ($\pm 5\%$).

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Influence of Fabrication Methods and Conditions on the Strengthening Effect and the Interfacial Adhesion

The amount of interfacial reactions depends on the chemical reactivity between fibre surfaces and matrix and is influenced by variation of fabrication temperature and residence time respectively. From viewpoint of the fibre surfaces, one has to distinguish between uncoated and coated boron fibres, and the both silicon carbide fibres, from that of the matrix between fabrication methods during which the matrix either remains in solid state or is molten, at least partially (compare fig.1).

Foil-Filament Process (AlF). From viewpoint of controllability of the interfacial reactions this solid state process is more suitable than such with molten aluminum because the fabrication temperature can be varied in a wide range. Fig. 4 shows the effect of fabrication temperature on the translation of fibre strength.

Fig. 4

Translation of fibre strength in boron and silicon carbide fibre reinforced aluminum composites as function of the fabrication temperature

One recognizes directly the effect of interfacial reactions on fibre damage. From these results one can derive optimum temperatures for the fabrication of composites using the solid state foil-filament process:

Uncoated boron fibre	530 °C
SiC fibre on tungsten	540 °C
SiC coated boron fibre	560 °C
B ₄ C coated boron fibre	600 °C
SiC fibre on carbon	600 °C

The effect of interfacial reactions on the adhesion between fibres and matrix is expressed by the measurable interlaminar shear strength and shown in fig. 5.

If one compares these shear stress data of the composites fabricated at the same temperature of 500 °C with results on fibre reactivity with the matrix (fig. 4 and table) one sees that the shear strength data are a mirror of the translation of fibre strength. The most reactive fibre-uncoated boron - exhibits the highest value of shear, the most inreactive fibre - SiC on carbon - the lowest.

The behaviour of the SiC_C-fibre is surprising if compared with the BSiC- and SiC_W-fibres. One would expect that SiC coated boron

Fig. 5

Shear strength of boron and silicon carbide fibre reinforced aluminum composites as function of the fabrication temperature

fibres will similar behave as SiC fibres. The deviation might be explained by the fact that the SiC_c-fibres have a surface layer enriched by carbon (3). If so, an aluminum carbide reaction layer is formed by reaction with the Al matrix which prevents further interfacial reactions and therefore fibre damage and interfacial adhesion respectively.

Diffusion Bonding Process Al_p. For our fabrication of model composites with this solid state technique only B₄C-coated boron fibres have been used in form of tapes with plasmasprayed aluminum alloy (AA 6061). The results are compiled in table 1.

FABRICATION TEMPERATURE, °C	600	600	630
TIME, min	30	10	30
FIBRE CONTENT %	42.5	42.5	43.6
FLEXURAL STRENGTH, MN/m ²	1847	1987	1625
TRANSLATION OF FIBRE STRENGTH, %	88	95	76
SHEAR STRENGTH, MN/m ²	113	89	117

Table 1: Relationship between translation of fibre strength and shear strength of BB₄C-fibre reinforced aluminum (diffusion bonding material of state "as fabricated")

The fabrication conditions at 600 °C with 30 min. residence time can be compared with those used in the foil-filament process (Al_p). Diffusion bonding technique results in a lower translation of fibre strength (88 to 97 %), but in a higher value of shear strength (113 to 85 MN/m²). These results indicate a higher reactivity of the matrix in diffusion bonding process which is caused, firstly, by the alloying components, and then, by the absence of impermeable skins of aluminum oxides within the interface.

A shortening of the residence time to 10 min. improves the translation of fibre strength, however, the shear strength is decreased and matrix failure occurs in shear test (comparable with fracture surface shown in fig. 6a).

In case of higher fabrication temperature (630 °C and 30 min) the translation of fibre strength is decreased considerably, but,

with only slight improvement of shear strength. The reduced composite strength is obviously caused by enhanced heating and thus fibre damage.

Braze Bonding Process (Al_B). Generally this technique is applied at temperature of $600^\circ C$ (4) because of the melting ranges of the matrix alloys (unmolten AA 6061 and molten brazing alloy AA4343). In our experiments SiC-coated and B_4C -coated boron fibres were used embedded in commercial plasmasprayed types.

The results are compiled in table 2, for both types of coated boron fibres.

F I B R E		BSiC	BB_4C
FIBRE CONTENT	%	54.3	46.0
FLEXURAL STRENGTH,	MN/m^2	1604	1628
TRANSLATION OF FIBRE STRENGTH,	%	88	93
SHEAR STRENGTH	MN/m^2	104	96

Table 2: Relationship between translation of fibre strength and shear strength of coated boron fibre reinforced aluminum (braze bonding material of state "as fabricated")

As seen before, the BSiC fibres are more reactive against the matrix than BB_4C fibres, and therefore composites result in higher shear strength value, but also in lower translation of fibre strength. Although the difference of these shear strength values seems to be neglectable, the failure behaviour during shear test indicates the insufficient adhesion between BB_4C fibres and matrix because of the failure occurs at the interface (fig. 6a). In case of BSiC fibres matrix failure is observed (fig.6b) indicating a strong adhesion between fibres and matrix.

Fig. 6: Fracture surface obtained by shear tests
a) BB_4C/Al_B b) $BSiC/Al_B$

As in case of BB_4C fibres a residence time of 10 min. at $600^\circ C$ seems to be too short to get a strong adhesion by the interfacial reactions, the influence of the extended time at fabrication temperature was studied (table 3). In fact, the shear strength values are increased, translation of fibre strength decreases. With all samples prepared by means of longer treatment times matrix failure occurs showing sufficient fibre/matrix adhesion.

Time at 600 °C	Mode of Failure	Shear Strength, MN/m^2		Translation of Fibre Strength %
		as fabr.	T6-treated	
10 min	interface	97	115	93
30 min	matrix	108	132	88
40 min	matrix	125	178	82
610 min	matrix	140	169	72

Table 3: Relationship between translation of fibre strength and shear strength of BB_4C -fibre reinforced aluminum (braze bonding material)

Liquid Infiltration Process (Al_T). The fabrication temperature is again limited at $600^\circ C$ because the matrix should melt only partially. The results are compiled in table 4.

F I B R E		BSiC	BB_4C	SiC_C	SiC_W
FIBRE CONTENT	%	50	48	46	49
FLEXURAL STRENGTH,	MN/m^2	1410	1893	1006	802
TRANSLATION OF FIBRE STRENGTH,	%	79	92	71	58
SHEAR STRENGTH,	MN/m^2	107	98	84	112

Table 4: Relationship between translation of fibre strength and shear strength of coated boron fibres and silicon carbide fibres reinforced aluminum (liquid infiltration material of state "as fabricated")

The values of the translation of fibre strength indicate again that the BB_4C fibre is most resistant against fibre damage during composite fabrication in which the fibres are directly contacted by molten matrix. Highest fibre damage is found with silicon carbide coated boron fibres as well as with the both silicon carbide fibres.

Analyses of the SiC_C fibre strength after contact with molten aluminum show that especially the coefficient of variation of fibre strength is considerably increased (from 16 to 27 %), whereas the mean value is decreased by only 5 %.

CONCLUSIONS

Sufficient interfacial adhesion between coated boron fibres and aluminum matrix causes a limited decrease of fibre strength in the order of magnitude of 10 %. In case of the treatable alloy AA 6061 sufficient adhesion means shear strengths of 105 - 115 MN/m² in the state "as fabricated" and of 130 - 135 MN/m² in the state "T6-treated". Further improvement of these shear strength is possible, but causes an increased fibre damage.

B₄C-coated boron fibre seems to be most suitable for a high strengthening effect and sufficient interfacial adhesion because of the limited interfacial reactions. SiC-coated boron fibres are more reactive and therefore the fabrication process is more difficult to control. Also uncoated boron fibres can be used for successful reinforcement but only within small limits of strictly controlled fabrication conditions. The SiC fibre on carbon shows the disadvantage of poor adhesion with aluminum matrix, the SiC fibre on tungsten that of fibre damaging reactions between SiC core and tungsten substrate.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors thank Dr. H. LEIS, Messerschmitt-Bölkow-Blohm, (München) and Mr. R. KOCHENDÖRFER, DFVLR (Stuttgart) for experimental support. The work was financed by the German Department of Defence.

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